

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE CONSUMERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING

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Abstract

The entire economic picture has changed after the breakout of Covid-19. The global economy has been severely impacted by this pandemic. The combination of government restrictions and the risk of becoming infected has resulted in the forward move towards online shopping. This article aims to look at how consumer behaviour has shifted toward online shopping with the introduction of Covid-19, as well as purchase habits for specific items from e-commerce businesses. According to the findings, Covid-19 has a significant impact on online shopping, as 66.43 % of respondents have increased their online shopping tendencies. According to the findings, Covid-19 has a substantial impact on mobile phones, clothing, food grains, and household items, but slightly impacts furniture and electronic devices. According to the findings, 61 % of respondents would prefer to buy more online once the pandemic is over. The findings could help consumers and retailers make judgments during a pandemic.

Keywords: Online Shopping, Consumer Perception, Covid-19, Post-pandemic, In-store shopping

Introduction

Online shopping sites contain a wide variety of goods both high quality and mild quality keeping in mind the level of people.

Covid-19 has put the global economy downward, many sectors have witnessed a huge downfall in their sales and profit while some sectors got benefited from it. The E-commerce sector is one of those sectors which have witnessed an upsurge from the Covid-19. The risk of getting infected from global pandemic Covid-19 and government restrictions has surged many consumers to move towards online shopping. **(Aggarwal & Kapoor, 2020)** People are changing what they purchase, where and how, from conventional buying to online shopping. Due to the increased risk of coronavirus, customers avoid public places, increasing customers' attraction towards online shopping. **(Sarode, 2015)** Online shopping is altering the way people buy and sell goods and services. E-commerce is the way of the future when it comes to shopping. The gap between the manufacturer and the consumer has narrowed as a result of online shopping.

(Hartono, et al., 2021) Uncovers fresh information about customers' adaptive behaviour and attitudes as a result of the Covid -19 pandemic; for example, shoppers who are more sensible, economical, and health-conscious are more ready to donate and use online shopping. Shoppers who fall into the category of "non-panic, young, and all-around adapters" and "rich, young, and non-price sensitive adapters" are more likely to use a combination of factors to change their purchasing attitudes and behaviour. Government restrictions on the opening of malls and stores have also forced many consumers to move online to purchase a product.

(Sehgal, Khanna, Malviya, & Dubey, 2021) The COVID-19 pandemic has changed people's buying habits all around the world. Staying at home, social isolation, and personal hygiene are all factors for such changes. COVID-19 affects customers' daily lives; the effect of lockdown and social distancing has influenced consumers' shopping and purchasing patterns. Consumers are picking up on new buying habits. While shopping during the COVID-19 pandemic, customers are extremely cautious about their safety. Covid-19 outbreak has forced many people and businesses to go online. **(Mehta, Saxena, & Purohit, 2020)** Online ready-to-eat food delivery services switched over to providing necessities like fruits, vegetables, and groceries overnight.

Online Shopping

The global economy is rapidly adapting to digital technology. (**Internet World Stats 2021**) As of June 2021, 65.6 % of the world's population has access to the internet. With the upsurge in internet users around the world, so does the rise in the number of online shopping audiences. A large selection of products, online shopping 24 hours a day, quick exchange and return, contactless payments, and no-touch delivery are some of the primary aspects that encourage people to purchase online. (**Sunitha & Gnanadhas, 2014**) Online shopping sites contain a wide variety of goods both high quality and mild quality keeping in mind the level of people. Hike in internet users and a rising standard of living is moving the economy towards digital adaption resulting in a boost to online shopping.

(**Rastogi, 2010**) Attitude toward online shopping and goal to shop online is not only affected by ease of use, usefulness, and enjoyment, but also by other factors like consumer individuality, situational factors, product distinctiveness, previous online shopping understanding and faith in online shopping. E-commerce sellers are taking Covid-19 as an advantage to capture the market of physical stores. Contactless delivery and shopping at their convenience are the main key drivers that e-commerce operators are using to attract consumers. (**Kim & Li, 2009**) Buyers typically use online platforms to discover relevant information and purchase products with minimal time and effort. The precise, relevant, and up-to-date information provided by e-commerce platforms will save shoppers time and energy spent on seeking information, allowing them to have more satisfaction.

Review of Literature

(**East, 2022**) In a study predicted that online grocery purchases will fall back in the post-pandemic period is conditional on an effective end to the pandemic. This study suggests that with relaxation in Covid-19 restriction there will be a decline in Online grocery purchases and customers will move backwards towards physical store shopping. It suggests that supermarkets have to enhance their strategies to attract customers back in store.

(**Rao, Saleem, Saeed, & Haq, 2021**) Suggests that consumers feel more satisfied when shopping from an online store than from a physical store. This study states that the e-commerce sector received an upsurge from the Covid-19. Consumers are more confident while buying a good from an online store and their satisfaction levels are very high from online shopping compared to in-store shopping.

(**Bhatti, et al., 2020**) In a study explained the effect of the covid-19 outbreak on the global economy. They suggest that the e-commerce sector has taken the advantage of Covid-19 by fulfilling the demand of consumers. As per this study more than 50%, of consumers are avoiding going for physical shopping and crowded places as there is risk of getting infected while doing shopping physically in a store. As per this study consumers prefers to shop online during pandemic.

(**Shetty & Pai, 2020**) Covid-19 has adversely affected the economy, some sectors have been really hard hit, but some benefited from it as they have received a boost by selling online. This study suggests that online stores should identify the trends in the economy to gain benefit. This study explains that lockdown had a large impact on the e-commerce sector and digital adaption has played a vital role in influencing consumer behaviour towards online shopping.

(**Hasanat, et al., 2020**) Suggest that online businesses are facing problems as they import raw material for finished goods from China but after the emergence of Covid-19 and lockdown, they are unable to import raw material which results in their supply. It also explains that Covid-19 has decreased the growth of the economy as operators are not able to supply goods due to the unavailability of raw materials for finished goods.

(**Maat & Konings, 2018**) Explains that regular internet users prefer to shop online more compared to irregular internet users. This study suggests that women prefer to shop more online nowadays and they especially prefer to shop for clothes online. When comparing the share of online shopping to retail shopping, it was discovered that online shoppers with limited access to stores purchased more online.

(**Prashar, Vijay, & Parsad, 2017**) The E-commerce sector is witnessing an upsurge. This expansion has been fueled by rapid technological adoption, rising living standards, an ageing population, a growing middle class, and increased Internet access via broadband and the use of smartphones and tablets. This study shows that shopping values and web ambient signals have no direct impact on purchase intentions.

Rather, these antecedent characteristics act as sources of gratification, influencing purchase intent as a result.

(Rastogi, 2010) A study explained that male buyers prefer more online shopping than female buyers. It also suggests that buyer prefers to buy online but while doing payment most buyers prefer to pay via Cash on Delivery mode rather than online payments. This study suggests that buyers prefer to buy online as they get a variety of products at lower prices.

Objectives of Study

1. To identify the changes in consumer perception towards online shopping after the emergence of Covid-19.
2. To identify the association between the gender of buyer and preference of suitable shopping mode.
3. To identify the association between the gender of the buyer and the impact of Covid-19 on Online shopping pattern.
4. To identify the factors which influence consumer behaviour towards online shopping.
5. To analyse the impact of Covid-19 on the purchase behaviour of select products.

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis has been framed for a study.

H01: There is no significant impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on consumers' perception toward online shopping.

H02: There is no association between the gender of the buyer and preference of suitable shopping mode.

H03: There is no association between the gender of the buyer and the impact of Covid-19 on Online shopping pattern.

Research Methodology

A structured questionnaire-based survey was used to collect data for this study. The questionnaires are distributed both online and offline, using a variety of platforms. The form received 140 responses, out of which 71 were Female and 69 Male. The impact of numerous aspects on consumers' perceptions of online purchasing was evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 equalling "strongly disagree" and 5 equalling "strongly agree." The respondents for the study were chosen using the convenience sampling approach.

The study's secondary data was gathered from a variety of newspapers, journals, and reports. To test the reliability of data Cronbach's alpha test was used and data was analysed using the SPSS. For testing of the Hypothesis Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test and Chi-square test has been used.

Analysis & Results

Demographic Profile of Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	69	40.3%
	Female	71	50.7%
Age-group	18-25 years	84	60%
	26-32 years	42	30%
	33-40 years	8	5.7%
	Above 40 years	6	4.3%
Level Of Education	Intermediate	16	11.4
	Graduate	31	22.1%
	Post Graduate	66	47.2%
	M.Phil & PhD	27	19.3%
Monthly Income	Up to Rs.20,000	79	56.4%
	Rs. 20,000 40,000	44	31.4%
	Rs. 40,000 – 60,000	7	5%
	Above Rs. 60000	10	7.2%

Table 1 – Demographic profile of Respondents.

Data was gathered from 140 respondents out of which 71 were female and 69 males. Most of the population size is young as 60 % of respondents belong to the 18 – 25 years and 30 % belong to the 26 – 32 years. In terms of the level of education, most of the respondents (47.2 %) had a post-graduate degree.

Frequency	Before Covid-19	Percentage	After the emergence of Covid -19	Percentage
Once in a Month	76	54.29 %	38	27.14 %
Two times a month	39	27.86 %	22	15.71 %
Three times a Month	15	10.71 %	33	23.57 %
Four times a Month	8	5.71 %	28	20 %
Five times a Month	2	1.43 %	19	13.58 %
Total	140	100 %	140	100 %

Table 2 – Frequency of online shopping in a month before and after the emergence of Covid-19

The goal was to determine respondents' online shopping behaviour before and after the outbreak of Covid-19. The findings indicate that online purchasing has increased slightly since the Covid-19 outbreak. Following the Covid-19 outbreak, 23.57 % of respondents prefer to buy three times a month, compared to 10.71% previously, 20% prefer to buy four times a month, compared to 5.71 % previously, and 13.58 % prefers to buy five times or more in a month, compared to 1.43 % previously.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid-19	140	1.74	.970	1	5
Online Shopping After emergence of Covid-19	140	2.77	1.395	1	5

Table 3 – Descriptive Statistics for Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

Ranks

	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Online Shopping After emergence of Covid19 - Negative Ranks	13 ^a	35.69	464.00
Online Shopping After emergence of Covid19 - Positive Ranks	86 ^b	52.16	4486.00
Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid19 - Ties	41 ^c		
Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid19 - Total	140		

a. Online Shopping After emergence of Covid19 < Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid19

b. Online Shopping After emergence of Covid19 > Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid19

c. Online Shopping after emergence of Covid19= Online Shopping Before emergence of Covid19

Test Statistics^a

	Online Shopping After Covid - Online Shopping Before Covid
Z	-7.137 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks.

H01: There is no significant impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on consumers' perception toward online shopping.

As per result P Value is less than the 0.05%, so we reject the null hypothesis. Results suggest that there is significant impact of Covid-19 on Consumer's perception towards online shopping. As per results consumer perception towards online shopping has been increased after the emergence of Covid-19.

Effect on shopping pattern	Frequency	Percentage
Increase in Online Shopping	93	66.43 %
Decrease in Online Shopping	13	9.28 %
No Impact	34	24.29 %
Total	140	100 %

Table 4 – Effect of Covid-19 on online shopping pattern.

The goal was to see how Covid-19 affected online shopping habits. The findings indicate that Covid-19 had a favourable impact on online shopping, with 66.43 % of respondents reporting an increase in online shopping, 24.29 % reported no impact, and 9.28 % reported a decrease in online shopping.

Chart 1 – Average monthly online shopping expenses before and after the Covid-19 outbreak.

The objective is to determine respondents' typical monthly spending on online shopping and the impact of Covid-19 on their average monthly spending on online shopping. The findings imply that Covid-19 has a beneficial impact on online buying, as respondents' average monthly expenses on online shopping have grown. 43.57 % of respondents spent an average of Rs.3000–6000 per month, up from 20.71 % previously.

Table 5 – gender wise impact of Covid-19 on online shopping pattern.

	Male	Female	Total
Increase In Shopping	41	52	93
Decrease in Shopping	9	4	13
No Impact	19	15	34
Total	69	71	140

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.667	2	.160
Likelihood Ratio	3.721	2	.156
No. of Valid Cases	140		

Table 6 – Chi-square test on Gender and impact of Covid-19 on online shopping pattern of respondents.

H02: - There is no association between the gender of buyers and the impact of Covid-19 on online shopping pattern.

- As per results P value is greater than the 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted.
- The findings indicate that there is no significant association between buyers' gender and the impact of Covid-19 on their online shopping pattern.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
Online shopping is safe and convenient after the outbreak of Covid19	40	70	19	11	0	3.99	3.56
Prices of products are less on online platforms as compared to in-store.	18	61	39	17	5	3.5	3.12
Preferred to shop online as delivery partners are following Contactless delivery	24	65	39	10	2	3.71	3.29
Preferred to shop online as there is a risk of being infected while shopping physically.	29	76	23	11	1	3.86	3.44

Table 7 – Consumers' perception toward online shopping during Covid outbreak.

The reliability of data is analysed using Cronbach's alpha test and the calculated value is 0.715. Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher is widely regarded as acceptable.

The findings reveal that during the Covid-19 outbreak, respondents strongly agree that online shopping is safe and convenient as compare to shopping physically in a store. It also reveals that customers agree that they prefer to shop online as product prices are lower on online platforms than in physical stores. During the Covid spread, the majority of respondents agreed that they preferred to purchase online because delivery executives adhere to contactless delivery guidelines and there is a chance of getting infected while physically shopping in a store.

	Before Covid-19			After the emergence of Covid-19		
	Most of Times	Sometimes	Never	Most of Times	Sometimes	Never
Mobile	50	58	32	62	42	36
Clothes	32	91	17	57	77	6
Food Grains & Grocery	14	62	64	36	64	40
Electronics	11	45	84	15	52	73
Furniture	3	21	116	8	31	101
Household items	20	80	40	35	84	21

Chart 2 – Factors that influenced the consumer’s perception for online purchasing over in-store shopping during the Covid-19 epidemic.

The goal is to determine which factors influence consumer preference for online shopping over in-store shopping during the Covid-19 outbreak.

The results suggest that shopping at own convenience (36.4%), easy return & exchange (30 %) are the primary variables driving respondents' online shopping behaviour during the Covid-19 outbreak followed by easy return & exchange (20%) and Contactless Delivery (13.60%).

Table 8 – Respondent’s perception toward different products before and after emergence of Covid-19.

	Male	Female	Total
Online Shopping	46	51	97
Physical in-store Shopping	23	20	43
Total	69	71	140

The aim was to see how Covid-19 affected certain items. According to the findings, Covid-19 has a significant impact on consumer perceptions of online purchasing for mobile phones, clothing, food grains, and home items, while having a minor impact on electronic items and furniture. During the covid outbreak, respondents prefer to buy more clothes, food grains, and household items online, but they still prefer physical stores for electronic equipment (air conditioners, refrigerators, coolers, televisions), and furniture. Covid-19 has improved consumer perceptions toward online shopping for mobile phones, clothing, food grains, and home items, but not for furniture or electronic devices.

Chart 3 – Preferred mode of payment for online shopping before and after the emergence of Covid-19
 The aim is to find out the impact of Covid-19 on the preferred mode of payment while shopping online. The findings imply that Covid-19 has had a favourable impact on online payment, since 79.29% prefer to pay online after the Covid-19 outbreak, compared to 39.28% previously. There is a significant drop

in the number of people who prefer Cash on Delivery as a payment method, with 20.71 % preferring Cash on delivery as a payment method compared to 60.72 % before Covid-19.

Table 9 – Respondent’s preference of shopping mode.

H03: - There is no association between the gender of buyers and preference of shopping mode.

X^2	0.43855	Degree Of Freedom	1
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Table 10 – Chi-square test on Gender of buyers and preference of shopping mode.

- At 5% significance level and 1 degree of freedom the table value of Chi-square is 3.84145.
- As per results Calculated value (0.43855) < Table Value (3.84145). Hence null hypothesis is accepted.
- The results suggest that there is no association between the gender of buyers and preference of shopping mode.

Chart 4 - Consumer behaviour after end of Covid-19

The goal is to examine the respondent's behaviour following the Covid era. According to the findings, 61% of respondents will prefer to shop more online in the future, while 39% will switch towards shopping in physical stores after Covid-19 ends. According to the findings, Covid-19 will have a positive influence on customers' perceptions toward online shopping.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic has a positive impact on consumers' perception toward online shopping. The result of the study states that 66.43% have witnessed an upsurge in their shopping pattern in a month. The findings suggest that Covid-19 has a significant impact on online buying, as respondents' average monthly online shopping expenses have increased. The convenience of shopping at one's leisure, 24/7 accessibility, contactless delivery, and simple exchange & return are the key factors that have influenced consumer perceptions of online shopping during the pandemic. Respondents preferred to buy more clothes, food grains, and home items online during the Covid outbreak, but they still prefer to buy electrical appliances and furniture in physical stores. According to the statistics, Covid-19 had a positive impact on preferring online payment as payment mode while shopping online, as 79.29% choose to pay online after the outbreak, compared to 39.28% previously. Respondents' post-pandemic behaviour suggests that 61% of respondents will prefer to shop more online once the pandemic ends, while 39 % will return to physical stores. Respondents prefer to shop online during the covid outbreak as there

is a risk of getting infected while shopping physically in a store, and online shopping is safe and convenient during the pandemic.

Limitation of Study

There are many factors which influencing consumers perception towards online shopping but this study is limited to study the impact of Covid-19 on online shopping. Some consumers prefer to shop most frequently in a month but this study is limited to shopping frequency 5 Times a month in a month. Study was basically focused on the young consumers. 140 respondents were selected from the vast population of online shoppers.

References

- Aggarwal, B., & Kapoor, D. (2020). A Study on Influence of COVID-19 pandemic on customer's online buying behavior. *I(2)*, 41-47.
- Bhatti, A., Akram, H., Basit, H. M., Khan, A. U., Mahwish, S., Naqvi, R., & Bilal, M. (2020). E-commerce trends during COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Future Generation Communication and Networking*, *13(2)*, 1449-1452.
- East, R. (2022). Online Grocery Sales after the Pandemic. *International Journal of Market Research*, *64(1)*, 13-18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/14707853211055047>
- Hartono, A., Ishak, A., Abdurrahman, A., Astuti, B., Marsasi, E. G., Ridanasti, E., . . . Muhammad, S. (2021). COVID-19 Pandemic and Adaptive Shopping Patterns: An Insight from Indonesian Consumers. *Global Business Review*, 1-19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509211013512>
- Hasanat, M. W., Hoque, A., Shikha, F. A., Anwar, M., Hamid, A. A., & Huam, T. H. (2020). The Impact of Coronavirus (Covid-19) on E-Business in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, *3(1)*, 85-90. Retrieved from <https://asianjournal.org/online/index.php/ajms/article/view/219/100>
- Kim, Y. G., & Li, G. (2009). Customer satisfaction and loyalty of online travel products: A transaction cost economics perspective. *Tourism Economics*, *15*, 825-846. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5367/000000009789955125>
- Maat, K., & Konings, R. (2018). Accessibility or Innovation? Store Shopping Trips versus Online Shopping. *Transportation Research Record*, *2672(50)*, 1-10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198118794044>
- Mehta, S., Saxena, T., & Purohit, N. (2020). *Journal of Health Management*, *22(2)*, 291-301. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0972063420940834>
- Prashar, S., Vijay, T. S., & Parsad, C. (2017). Effects of Online Online Shopping Values and Website Cues on Purchase Behaviour: A Study Using S-O-R Framework. *The Journal for Decision Makers*, *42(1)*, 1-18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090916686681>
- Rao, Y., Saleem, A., Saeed, W., & Haq, J. U. (2021). Online Consumer Satisfaction During COVID-19: Perspective of a Developing Country. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *12*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.751854>
- Rastogi, A. K. (2010). A study of Indian online consumers & their buying behaviour. *Research Analysis and Evaluation*, *1(10)*, 80-82.
- Sarode, R. M. (2015). Future of E-Commerce in India Challenges & Opportunities. *International Journal of Applied Research*, *1(12)*, 646-650. Retrieved from <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/2015/vol1issue12/PartJ/1-12-83.pdf>
- Sehgal, R., Khanna, P., Malviya, M., & Dubey, A. M. (2021). Shopping Safety Practices Mutate Consumer Buying Behaviour during COVID-19 Pandemic. *Vision*, 1-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629211010990>
- Shetty, S., & Pai, R. (2020). Impact of covid-19 on online shopping -a case study. *Shetty, Sahana & Pai, Ramesh. (2021). IMPACT OF COVID-19 EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management*, 9-15. doi:10.36713/epra7063
- Sunitha, C. K., & Gnanadhas, M. E. (2014). Online Shopping - An Overview. *B-Digest*, *6*, 16-22.
- Internet World Stats (2021). Internet usage statistics: The Internet big picture. <https://www.internetworldstats.com/stats.htm>